

Integrated Photonics Micro-Ring Resonator Design for Scalable Quantum Photonics Information Processing: A Way Towards Fault-Tolerant Continuous Variable Quantum Computing

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Integrated Photonics shows promise as a platform for realizing quantum computing. Discovering an optimized architecture for this platform could enable us to solve problems that make challenges for classical computers. One such problem is finding the hafnian of a matrix, which is a #P – hard problem. Gaussian Boson Sampling (GBS) provides a viable method for demonstrating quantum computational advantage and mathematical connections to some specific graph-related and quantum chemistry problems. Using the samples generated from GBS has been proposed to solve classical stochastic algorithms in the search for certain graph features. This research represents a step toward testing real-world problems using existing noisy intermediate-scale quantum computers. It aims to promote the development of a more efficient platform for implementing quantum algorithms. The simulation results have been done by the full-wave FDTD (Finite Difference Time Domain) method collaborated with Lumerical Solutions. The verification of these results can be obtained acceptably by comparing these simulated results with the practical Xanadu Quantum Photonic Computer ones.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is safe to assume that the era of quantum information and computation started to gain momentum with Richard Feynman's proposal of quantum simulators¹, alongside Paul Benioff^{2,3} and David Deutsch's⁴ investigation of its feasibility and theoretical aspects.

In a renowned work from the mid-90s, Peter Shore highlighted the vulnerability of widely employed public key encryption techniques such as Elliptic Curve Cryptography and RSA to quantum computers⁵. Interestingly, an effective countermeasure against this threat involves the utilization of Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) protocols^{6–8}, which remain

immune due to the no-cloning theorem governing quantum states⁹.

Over the past couple of decades, the realms of quantum computation and telecommunications have captivated the imagination of researchers and scientists alike. The promise of harnessing the peculiar principles of quantum mechanics for ultra-fast computation and secure communication has fueled extensive exploration. Similarly, the concept of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) has been a subject of interest for a considerable duration¹⁰. However, it is only in recent years that a confluence of these visionary ideas has given rise to practical applications. The synergy of quantum computation, telecommunications, and Photonic Integrated Circuits has opened up unprecedented possibilities, presenting a paradigm shift in how we approach information processing and communication technologies.

One such effort in utilizing Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) for advancing quantum computation was spearheaded by a group from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)¹¹. What they designed consists of a mesh of 88 generalized Mach-Zehnder Interferometers that can be programmatically controlled on microsecond timescales. This means that the characteristics of the Mach-Zehnder Interferometers, i.e. their respective quantum operations, can be dynamically adjusted according to the experimental requirements. The initial purpose of these photonic integrated circuits was to provide a platform for studying quantum transport in the presence of disorder. However, this specific experiment was demonstrated just as a proof of concept, and the potential of such structure to be used for quantum computation and artificial intelligence is further discussed in¹².

An exemplary illustration of the application of Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) in the realm of quantum computation is embodied in the X8 chip developed by Xanadu¹³. This product performs different quantum algorithms by harnessing the features of eight modes of squeezed states of light and 4-mode interferometers. The X8 chip not only showcases the practical integration of these functionalities, but also demonstrates its potential for quantum information processing. By utilizing the inherent properties of squeezed states of light, the X8 chip is designed to execute complex quantum opera-

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tions, including Gaussian boson sampling, molecular vibronic spectra, and graph similarity computations.

Building upon our team's prior investigations into the aforementioned chips and their proper light sources^{14,15}, we have drawn inspiration from these models to propose novel architectures with specific applications. In our research, we have focused on leveraging the potential of these PICs for tasks such as the teleportation of squeezed states of light¹⁶ and Gaussian Boson Sampling¹⁷.

In this study, by amalgamating insights gained from the analysis of existing chips, we introduce an integrated quantum photonic circuit design to implement Gaussian boson sampling which can be used in solving different problems such as graph problems¹⁸⁻²¹, quantum chemistry²², etc. We believe our work has the potential to push quantum photonics platforms one step ahead toward scalable universal quantum computation to implement continuous variable algorithms.

The behavior of nonlinear optical processes and the main basics of the theory and design for micro-ring resonators are explained in section II to show how they can work effectively. Section III presents the results of a single optical ring resonator in both normal state and squeezed state signaling. Some parameters will be described in section IV, such as the average noise reduction factor (NRF) score and its standard deviation to indicate more about the analysis of the X8 Quantum Photonics Processor. Finally, this research will be concluded in section V.

II. THEORY AND DESIGN

Light is a unique source and medium for employment in quantum technology applications, especially for quantum photonic computers (QPCs). Quantum computation requires high-quality scalable equipment for producing the desired squeezed light which is a substantial entity for many photonic quantum information processing applications, especially in Quantum Photonic Computers (QPCs). Most of these quantum devices need a scalable squeezed light source to enhance the stable and high throughput optical applications near the quantum limit. The single photon sources and detectors are the important parts of implementation in any quantum application of linear optics.

There are two main types of nonlinear optical process varieties²³:

1- Second Harmonic Generation (SHG), χ^2 processes

2- Four-wave mixing, χ^3 processes

Silicon has the capability of a large third-order nonlinear coefficient that enables photon-pair generation by spontaneous four-wave mixing (SFWM) which is a scattering process in which two pump photons (ω_p) are annihilated, creating a pair of photons at lower (ω_l) and higher energies (ω_s).

An optical parametric oscillator (OPO) is based on a pump or input signal that oscillates or resonates in the optical frequencies. This oscillator is a laser beam input nominated as a pump that can be converted to two lower frequency waves i.e. through second-order nonlinear optical interaction. The

relation between these angular frequencies is as follows:

$$n\omega_p = \omega_s + \omega_l \quad (1)$$

These two output signals are "Signal" and "Idler" in which the upper-frequency wave is the "Signal".

The relationships between Pump, Signal, and Idler can be defined for three-wave (3WM) and four-wave mixing (4WM) with $n=1$ and $n=2$, correspondingly.

A special case for these oscillators ($n=1$) is when the output frequency is half of the pump signal which results in half-harmonic generation when both signals have the same polarization.

As it has been indicated, these types of oscillators are used for coherent light sources and squeezed light generation for quantum processors and signal amplifications and photon conversion efficiency to optical signals properly.

The selection of Signal and Idler is one of the most important characteristics of phase matching for squeezing in the Ring Resonators. This property can be improved by changing and incrementing the (internal) rings.

The light incidence through the waveguide can couple to the resonant mode within the ring resonator. Resonance wavelength occurs when light accumulates a phase shift of 2π when it has the complete round trip in the ring (its circumference):

$$k_0 n_{eff} L = 2\pi m \quad (2)$$

where it can be written as:

$$f_{res} = \frac{mc_0}{n_{eff}L} \quad (3)$$

Where the f_{res} is the resonance frequency, m is the mode for the frequency, c_0 is the light speed, n_{eff} is the refractive index, and L is the length of the resonator. So, the optical ring resonator resonates when the optical path length of the ring is equal to the integral multiple of the wavelength.

Micro-ring resonators (MRRs) are a type of Silicon Photonic component in the form of waveguides including an optical path and an adjacent closed loop. These types of devices allow for specific frequencies of light to be trapped inside the ring and subsequently filtered out from the main optical path. In 1969, Marcatilli first proposed the idea of optical waveguide ring resonators and their applications in integrated optics²⁴. These resonators were not in the case of practical forms until the development of low-loss high-index optical waveguides²⁵. After this era, the fabricating of the ring resonators became more feasible, and it had a great interest in growing new applications such as wavelength (de)multiplexers, modulators, filters, and lasers which were proposed in²⁶.

There are several applications for ring resonators as follows: Cavity Quantum Electrodynamics^{27,28}, Differential Amplifiers²⁹, High-Resolution Spectroscopy³⁰, Disk Lasers³¹, Laser Frequency Stabilization³², Bistable Optical Elements³³, Sensors³⁴, Optical Communication³⁵, Optical Computing³⁶, Interferometric Sensing³⁷, Gyroscopes³⁸, Pressure & Vibration Sensing³⁹, Dispersion Compensation⁴⁰, Resonant Routing⁴¹, All Optical Processing (NL)⁴², ON-OFF Switches⁴³, Channel Dropping Filters⁴⁴, WDM

FIG. 1. Top view of the model for a single-bus ring resonator waveguide to define its electric field components
 κ : Coupling Coefficient
 t : Transmission Coefficient
 $*$: Complex Conjugate of the Coefficient

(De)Multiplexers⁴⁵, Polarization Rotators⁴⁶, Wavelength Converters⁴⁷, and Delay Lines^{48,49}.

Two models can be presented for a single-bus and double-bus ring resonator based on the theory indicated in⁵⁰ which the configuration of the ring resonator consists of a unidirectional coupling between a ring and a waveguide. This is the best way for the generation of photon pairs.

The ideal models are described by the coupling process between the ring and its waveguide assuming that there is only a single dominant mode with a single polarization state with the waveguide/ring composite at any given time. There is no coupling loss for the waveguide/ring component. The interaction of the electromagnetic fields between the waveguide/ring composites can be illustrated by the following matrix equations and the depicted Figures 1 and 2:

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_{t1} \\ E_{t2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t & \kappa \\ -\kappa^* & t^* \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_{i1} \\ E_{i2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The light has a reciprocal property that the ring operates identically in both input directions. This subject consequents in the matrix being symmetric and enforces the following equation:

$$|t|^2 + |\kappa|^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

Where $|t|^2$ and $|\kappa|^2$ are often called power transmission and power coupling coefficients.

In the photonics scope, the expression of (5) needs to be reduced in terms of P_{t1} , the transmitted power and P_{t2} , and the circulating power. This is accomplished by assigning the input electric field, E_{i1} to be equal to 1. The circulating electric fields, E_{i2} and E_{t2} are related to one another via a loss term and phase change as follows:

$$E_{i2} = A.e^{j\phi} E_{t2} \quad (6)$$

Where A is the loss coefficient, which is a summation of the propagation loss, absorption loss, and radiative loss of the

waveguide comprising the ring. The propagation loss is a result of sidewall roughness, whereas the absorption loss and radiative loss are a result of impurities in the silicon via dopants and bends in the waveguides, respectively. The phrase term ω is defined as $\phi = \frac{\omega L}{c}$. Here, ω refers to the angular frequency, L is the circumference of the ring, and c is the phase velocity speed of light in silicon. The angular frequency can be further expressed as $\omega = kc_0$, where k is the vacuum wavenumber and c_0 is the vacuum speed of light which is related to the aforementioned phase velocity speed of light in a medium by $c = c_0 n_{eff}$. Lastly, the vacuum wavenumber is related to the wavelength as $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$. To proceed, a key constant used in photonics is introduced known as the propagation constant, which is defined as:

$$\beta = k.n_{eff} \quad (7)$$

The effects on the phase due to the roundtrip propagation can be expressed as:

$$\phi = \omega L/c = (kc_0 L)/c = k.n_{eff}.L = \beta L \quad (8)$$

Now, the terms in the matrix relation (4) can be written as:

$$E_{t1} = \frac{-A + t.e^{-j\beta L}}{-At^* + e^{-j\beta L}} \quad (9)$$

$$E_{i2} = \frac{-A\kappa^*}{-At^* + e^{-j\beta L}} \quad (10)$$

$$E_{t2} = \frac{\kappa^*}{1 - At^*e^{j\beta L}} \quad (11)$$

At this point, the electric field components can be related to their powers by applying an absolute square. This results in the following expressions for P_{t1} , the transmitted power, and P_{t2} , the circulating power:

$$P_{t1} = |E_{t1}|^2 = \frac{A^2 + |t|^2 - 2A|t|\cos(\beta L + \phi)}{1 + A^2|t|^2 - 2A|t|\cos(\beta L + \phi)} \quad (12)$$

$$P_{t2} = |E_{t2}|^2 = \frac{A^2(1 - |t|^2)}{1 + A^2|t|^2 - 2A|t|\cos(\beta L + \phi)} \quad (13)$$

Where $|t|$ and ϕ represent the magnitude and phase of the transmission coefficient, respectively. As previously mentioned, the complete derivation is presented in⁵¹. These equations demonstrate a cyclical behavior that produces a resonance in the powers when $\beta L + \phi = 2\pi m$ (an integer multiple of 2π) after a complete round-trip, where m is an integer as the mode number. If the effective refractive index (n_{eff}) is independent of wavelength, the length of the ring (circumference) is an integer multiple of the effective wavelength on resonance, or $L_{ring} = N \left(\frac{\lambda_0}{n_{eff}} \right)$, where the effective refractive index is defined as $n_{eff} = c \frac{\beta}{\omega}$ and $\lambda_0 = \frac{c}{f_0}$ is the free-space

wavelength at the resonance frequency f_0 . Since the resonant condition is dependent on β , it is inherently dependent on wavelength as stated in Equation (7), which creates the characteristic resonant dips in the transmission spectra of ring resonators. At resonance, the power equations can be further simplified to:

$$P_{t1} = \frac{(A - |t|^2)}{(1 - A|t|^2)} \quad (14)$$

$$P_{i2} = \frac{A^2(1 - |t|^2)}{(1 - A|t|^2)} \quad (15)$$

There exists a special case when the circulating power equals the ring resonator internal loss, i.e. when $|\kappa|^2 = 1 - A^2$, or in the case of an ideal lossless coupler, it can also be expressed as $|t| = A$. In this special case, the transmitted power becomes 0. This effect is known as critical coupling and is often sought after as a targeted behavior when designing ring resonators.

The idealistic ring resonator spectrum shown here behaves like a Fabry-Perot interferometer and hence the standard figure of merits (FOMs) is used to characterize its behavior. These FOMs are the free spectral range (FSR), the full-width at half-maximum (FWHM), extinction ratio (ER), quality factor (Q), and insertion loss (IL). The spectral response of this idealistic ring resonator is highly sensitive to changes in κ , A , and β . Therefore, when considering a realistic model where A and n_{eff} , and hence β , are highly influenced by fabrication variations such as waveguide thickness/height and sidewall angle/roughness, it's evident that a fabricated ring resonator will be even more sensitive to variation. With this in mind, one can assume that any fabricated ring will almost certainly not behave as anticipated, thus, some method for adaptive real-time correction is required. This can either be done via thermal tuning⁵¹ or P-N depletion tuning⁵² where both methods alter n_{eff} , which shifts the resonant frequency to the desired location.

The intensity magnification factor of M , the ratio of circulating intensity to incident intensity, is given by equation (13):

$$M = \frac{I_2}{I_1} = \frac{(1 - t^2)A^2}{1 - 2tA\cos(\phi) + t^2A^2} \quad (16)$$

In a special case of $\phi=0$ and $A = 1$, it can be converted to:

$$M = \frac{1+t}{1-t} \quad (17)$$

This is the maximum ratio of circulating power to incident power that can be achieved in the case of $\phi=0$ and $A = 1$ which indicates the situation of the resonance between the incident light and the ring $\phi = m2\pi$ and the attenuation is negligible ($A = 1$). The circulating power exceeds the incident power by the factor of M in equations 16 and 17 which is very large for t close to the 1 (unity). The incident power required for a desired single-pass nonlinear phase shift is reduced according to this equation.

The phase transfer characteristics of the resonator indicate an additional enhancement.

FIG. 2. Top View of the model for Double bus ring resonator (add drop resonator)

κ : Coupling Coefficient

t : Transmission Coefficient

*: Complex Conjugate of the Coefficient

The effective phase shift for the resonator can be defined as the phase argument of the field transmission factor, which is the phase shift acquired by the light in crossing the coupler from ports 1 to 3 (Figures 1 and 2).

For the case of negligible attenuation, i.e. $A = 1$, the effective phase shift will be presented as shown here:

$$\phi_{eff} = \pi + \phi + 2\arctan \frac{t\sin(\phi)}{1 - t\cos(\phi)} \quad (18)$$

The finesse of an optical resonator is a measure of the scale of narrow resonances concerning their frequency distance. It means that the higher finesse has the sharper resonances. Theoretically, it is defined as the free spectral range or FSR (i.e., the fundamental mode spacing) divided by the bandwidth of the resonances or FWHM (i.e. full width at half-maximum):

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{FSR}{FWHM} \quad (19)$$

It depends on resonator losses and is independent of the resonator length.

The free spectral range (FSR) can be calculated as:

$$\Delta\lambda = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{L_{ring}n_g} = \frac{\lambda_0^2}{2\pi rn_g} \quad (20)$$

Where λ_0 is the central wavelength, L_{ring} is the circumference of the ring resonator, and $n_g = c(\frac{d\beta}{d\omega})$ is the group index.

The field enhancement can be defined as the ratio of $\frac{E_{r2}}{E_{i1}}$ as shown in the equation of (11).

Figure 3 shows the perspective view of the double-bus single-ring resonator. The free spectral range (FSR) and quality factor are the most important key parameters in the designing of ring resonators. They are responsible for the performance of this Silicon-based waveguide on the Silicon Dioxide

FIG. 3. Perspective View of Single Optical Ring Resonator (Scale in μm as Illustrated in Table I)

TABLE I. The Parameters and their Correspondence Values in FIG.3, Please note that the heights of Si and SiO₂ are $0.18\mu\text{m}$ and $4\mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
L	25	W	0.4
G	0.1	$L_{\text{Substrate}}$	25
R_{in}	3.106	$W_{\text{Substrate}}$	16
R_{out}	3.506		

(SiO₂) Substrate. The choice of waveguide spacing, coupling length, and ring length is crucial for the desired FSR and Q factor.

III. RESULTS, DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

Figure 3 shows the perspective view of a single optical ring resonator with one input port and three output ports which has a different form from Figure 2 having two input ports and two output ports.

Two states of signaling are analyzed for the optical ring resonator:

1- Normal state by using the port group for FDTD simulation in Lumerical Solutions

2- Squeezed state with pump and signal using the mode source for FDTD simulation in Lumerical Solutions

The first item triggering the input signal and observing the outputs through the port group has been illustrated in Figure

4.

For the optical micro-ring resonator, the resonance peaks can be found at $\approx 1.523\mu\text{m}$, $\approx 1.55\mu\text{m}$, and $\approx 1.577\mu\text{m}$ as shown in Figure 4.

Regarding Figures 5 and 6, the best values for parameters G and W are $0.1\mu\text{m}$ and $0.4\mu\text{m}$, correspondingly.

The values less than $0.4\mu\text{m}$ for W are not good enough for a transmission line performance in this case as illustrated in Figure 6.

In the second item, the pump and signal are triggered with different amplitudes.

The desired pump, signal, and idler frequencies are chosen as $f_p=193.4\text{THz}$ ($\approx \lambda_p=1550\text{nm}$ or $1.55\mu\text{m}$), $f_s=196.6\text{THz}$ ($\approx \lambda_s=1525\text{nm}$ or $1.525\mu\text{m}$), $f_i=190.2\text{THz}$ ($\approx \lambda_i=1576\text{nm}$ or $1.576\mu\text{m}$) concerning the satisfying of equation (1).

The amplitude of the pump and signal are considered as 10 and 5, correspondingly, and their phase is chosen to be 0.

Figure 7 shows the full profile of four-wave mixing (4WM). The pump and signal are detectable in this diagram. The magnitude of this full profile is changeable by tuning the G and W parameters.

Figure 8 illustrates the signal spectrums of the four ports in the squeezed state or four-wave mixing, distinctly.

IV. COMPARE TO X8 QUANTUM PHOTONICS PROCESSOR

Here, we review the experimental evaluation results that have been reported before⁵³ and then compare them with our

FIG. 4. Lumerical Results (Transmission) of Single Optical Ring Resonator Regarding the Dimensions Mentioned in Table I, Please Note that the Negative Value is due to the Direction of the Drop1 Signal for Reaching Port2 Concerning the Direction of the Other Signals

design. The primary element of the X8 quantum device comprises a $10 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm}$ photonic chip capable of generating squeezed light in up to eight distinct optical modes. This device was initially configured to produce four independent two-mode squeezed vacuum states. The chip facilitates two-mode squeezing between bichromatic mode pairs, each pair occupying one of four spatially separated waveguide modes.

An interferometer, constructed from a network of beam splitters and phase shifters, implements a user-programmable gate sequence representing a $SU(4)$ transformation (Figure 9) applied to the spatial modes. To define this transformation, the user needs to specify twelve independent real parameters, with the remaining three parameters representing irrelevant output phases. This transformation is applied to two four-mode subspaces distinguished by their optical wavelength. The resulting eight-mode programmable Gaussian state, synthesized by the chip, is then analyzed on the Fock basis using eight independent photon number-resolving (PNR) detectors. The chip is made of silicon nitride waveguides and thermo-optic phase shifters through a photolithographic process on

a specific wafer from Ligentec SA. It includes sections for pump light distribution, the creation of squeezed states, filters to segregate pump light from quantum signals, and customizable linear-optical transformations.

Four integrated squeezers based on micro-ring resonators generate bichromatic two-mode squeezed states in nearly singular temporal modes when activated by a pulsed laser. Each squeezer produces an entangled mode pair in its respective waveguide output, distinguished by wavelength as "Signal" and "Idler". Additionally, four Asymmetric Mach-Zehnder Interferometer (AMZI) filters separate pump light from squeezed states, directing the squeezed light into the programmable interferometer and the pump light out of the chip. The remaining pump light is monitored off-chip to stabilize the squeezer resonators.

The interferometer executes an arbitrary programmable four-mode linear optical transformation on both the signal and idler subspaces of the squeezed light. While the use of two-mode squeezers enhances the total number of modes available for detection per spatial mode, it restricts the range of accessible

FIG. 5. Lumerical Results (Transmission) of Single Optical Ring Resonator Using Port Group Regarding "G" Parameter Variations: (a) Through, and (b) Total Drop

eight-mode Gaussian states from the chip. Finally, the synthesized Gaussian state is extracted from the chip for photon counting.

The average noise reduction factor (NRF) score has been observed which shows the strength of the entanglement of the qumodes of the X8 quantum photonics processor. It is noteworthy that the lower NRF score is better. Notably, the standard deviation of the score is negligible (approximately 0.001). Upon closer examination, it has been observed that all values fall within the range of 0.85 to 0.9. Interestingly, these values are closer to those associated with uncorrelated photons (where no entanglement exists between states) rather than the full-entangled state. Moreover, the entanglement between different pairs of qumodes highlights that while photonic quantum computers show promise, they are not flawless in creating robust entanglement.

Experimental findings show a focus on the photon counts within qumode pairs across various configurations. Consis-

tent with previous results, the standard deviation in photon counts has minimal impact on the observed trends, whether the squeezing gates are in the OFF state (approximately 0.001) or the ON state (approximately 0.01).

Moreover, the observations show an increment in crosstalk effects. As the number of squeezing gates increases, cross-talk effects become more pronounced. The qumode pair that is switched OFF receives a greater number of photons as additional squeezing gates are activated. Notably, the variation in this trend across different qumode pairs highlights spatial dependencies in crosstalk.

Similarly, it has been reported the identification of substantial noise due to background effects (approximately 0.01) as well. Interestingly, this background noise is comparable to the impact of crosstalk resulting from nearby ON squeezing gates while idler qumodes are more susceptible to photon gain through crosstalk in comparison with their signal counterparts across all qumode pairs. Furthermore, Spatial and positional

(a)

(b)

FIG. 6. Lumerical Results (Transmission) of Single Optical Ring Resonator Using Port Group Regarding "W" Parameter Variations: (a) Through, and (b) Total Drop

differences play a role in how photons are redistributed.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an optical ring resonator was proposed to employ in the compact micro-chip of Quantum Photonics Computers (QPCs) with an optimized architecture to solve the problems that make challenges for traditional computers. This micro-ring resonator was analyzed by both normal and squeezed state signaling. Gaussian Boson Sampling (GBS) provided a more efficient platform for implementing quantum algorithms. The simulation results were done by the full-wave FDTD (Finite Difference Time Domain) method collaborated with Lumerical Solutions. The verification of these results was obtained acceptably by comparing these simulated results with the practical Xanadu Quantum Photonic Computer ones.

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FIG. 7. Lumerical Results (Squeezed State) for Transmission Coefficient of Single Optical Ring Resonator Regarding the Dimensions Mentioned in Table I, Please Note that the Negative Value is due to the Direction of the Signals

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(a)

(b)

FIG. 8. Results of Spectrum in Four-Wave Mixing (4WM) for Single Optical Ring Resonator, $f_p=193.4\text{THz}$, $f_s=196.6\text{THz}$, $f_i=190.2\text{THz}$

FIG. 9. X8, Representation of Distributed Circuit for Photonic Hardware with a Maximum Initial Eight Modes

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